

Institutional transformation and resilience in Brazilian democracy (2012-2025): polity, politics, and policy in interaction

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Cláudio Gonçalves Couto^I ,
Rogério Bastos Arantes^{II}

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ABSTRACT Introduction: Between 2012 and 2025, Brazilian democracy faced a series of crises that tested the foundations of presidentialism, the judicial system, and federalism. This article examines how these tensions produced institutional change and revealed the regime's resilience. The central argument is that understanding democracy under stress requires integrating three dimensions: *polity* (the rules and institutions that structure the regime), *politics* (political competition and conflict among actors), and *policy* (public policy decisions and outcomes). **Materials and methods:** The study adopts a historical institutionalist approach, employing process tracing to identify causal mechanisms that link critical events, institutional choices, and changes in actors' behavior. The 2012-2025 period is analyzed across three arenas: the system of government, the judiciary, and intergovernmental relations. **Results:** Three major transformations were identified. In the system of government, the National Congress expanded its veto and policymaking powers - particularly through budgetary control - consolidating a form of "congressional government." In the judiciary, the Supreme Federal Court (STF) broadened its protagonism: it redesigned political and electoral rules, ruled on the *Mensalão* scandal, and curtailed authoritarian initiatives under Bolsonaroism, protecting state and municipal powers in the process. Within the federalist system, and despite the absence of formal reforms, subnational governments assumed a more prominent role - especially during the pandemic - enhancing their autonomous capacities and intergovernmental cooperation, albeit at the cost of exacerbating territorial inequalities. **Discussion:** The political crises between 2012 and 2025 not only tested but ultimately strengthened Brazil's institutions, prompting lasting adaptations and institutional learning. The interaction among *polity*, *politics*, and *policy* reshaped the political system - both formally and informally - revealing democratic resilience even under the risk of authoritarian rupture and threats of a coup. This interpretive framework contributes to comparative studies of how democracies under stress can adapt, endure, and transform.

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I. Introduction¹

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² The 'Mensalão' was a major Brazilian political scandal uncovered in 2005, involving alleged monthly payments to lawmakers from parties within President Lula's governing coalition in exchange for congressional support. Although several coalition parties were implicated, the ruling Workers' Party (PT)

In just over a decade, Brazilian democracy has experienced successive crises that have tested and transformed its institutions: the 'Mensalão'² trial, the mass street protests that began in June 2013, the contestation of the 2014 election results, the impeachment of President Dilma Rousseff, Operation Car Wash, the election of a far-right populist in 2018, and his attacks on the democratic regime, the attempted coup on January 8, 2023, and, finally, the change in the conditions of interaction between the executive, legislative, and judicial branches, with the National Congress gaining prominence, the weakening of the presidency, and the expansion of the political powers of the Supreme Federal Court.

This process affected not only specific areas of Brazil's institutional structure but also had an impact on its central institutional pillars: the presidential system of government, the judicial system, and federalism. In this regard, two

was the most politically and publicly affected. The case was tried by the Supreme Federal Court, which convicted several political leaders for the crimes of corruption, embezzlement, and money laundering, but ultimately acquitted them all of the charge of forming a criminal organization.

aspects must be considered: first, how and why did institutions change? Second, how did they react and resist the challenges?

Seeking to answer these questions, this article aims to outline the main aspects that have affected the functioning of Brazilian democracy since 2012, focusing on institutional changes, the causes and effects of such changes, as well as the capacity of these same institutions to address governance problems, defend democracy itself, and produce public policies. The identification of processes of political crisis, institutional change, democratic recession, and institutional resilience is one of the main themes of contemporary political science, and the study of the Brazilian case can contribute to enriching the empirical elements and theoretical arsenal of comparative studies on phenomena that currently shake democracies.

We start from the theoretical assumption of Couto & Arantes in their analysis of constitutional politics and the relationship between constitutionalism and democracy (Arantes & Couto, 2010; Couto & Arantes, 2006), according to which democratic politics is structured in a complex relationship between three levels: the political game (*politics*), political institutions (*polity*), and the production of government decisions, or public policies (*policy*). Here, however, our scope goes beyond the constitutional question.

It is common in institutionalist political science to consider that *polity* overdetermines *politics* and *policy*. Or, following the path opened by Lowi (2015), that there is an interaction between *politics* and *policy*, since different arenas of power, involving different types of public policies, produce different types of political games - in simplified but well-established terms, *policy determines politics*. What the Brazilian case shows is that **the three political dimensions are mutually determined**. That is, **in different contexts**, and in a non-exclusive manner, not only *does policy determine politics*, but *politics also determines polity*, *polity determines politics*, *polity determines policy*, and even *policy determines polity*.

Based on this theoretical approach, we study the relationship between political and judicial actors and institutions in Brazil, more specifically the main processes of transformation and tests of resistance to which the three central institutional pillars of Brazilian democracy (presidential system of government, justice system, and federalism) were subjected between 2012 and 2025. The time frame is based on the existence, during this historical period, of important transformations and challenges, not always simultaneous, in each of the three pillars.

In 2012, the trial of the ‘Mensalão’ political corruption case marked the beginning of a transformation in the role of the judiciary, before changes in the other two areas. For this reason, we define this year as the beginning of the period to be studied.

A more in-depth methodological discussion is beyond the scope of this article. We will briefly point out our references in this regard. Guided by a historical institutionalist approach, the article reconstructs the period, identifying causal mechanisms embedded in institutional changes and the interaction between political actors. To this end, we use *process-tracing* methodology not only to detect the historical sequence of events, correlations between events, or potential causes and results, but also to examine the causal mechanics of the production of certain results (Beach & Pedersen, 2019; Mahoney, 2012). In the words of Perissinotto (2024, p. 11): “More than finding associations between variables, it is necessary to reveal the intermediate mechanisms that connect the cause to its effect, showing how correlations emerge.”

According to Beach (2020), the mechanisms of *process tracing* consist of entities and activities: “Entities are the factors (actors, organizations, or structures) engaging in activities, whereas the activities, are the producers of change or what transmits causal forces or powers through a mechanism” (Beach, 2020, p. 703). That is, once a cause and its result have been identified, it is necessary to identify and understand what connects them. In the final section of the article, devoted to the discussion of the case, we articulate these methodological categories with empirical analysis.

The in-depth study of a particular case, that of Brazil, allows us to observe causal mechanisms with greater precision. Its specificity allows us not only to better understand the specific case, but also to formulate useful hypotheses for the comparative study of democracies in which similar phenomena occur, albeit with different results. This is the advantage that such a research method provides us and the reason why we adopt it. This is the broader contribution of this work.

In addition to this introduction, the article is organized into five other sections. In the next section, we show how the Brazilian presidential coalition government system changed in the decade between 2015 and 2025, giving rise to new forms of relationship between the executive and legislative branches. In the third section, we address the transformation of the role of the Federal Supreme Court (STF) since the ruling on Criminal Action 470 ('Mensalão') in 2012 and its particularly important role as a force containing the authoritarian advances of the Jair Bolsonaro government. The fourth section deals with the tensions and crises in intergovernmental relations in Brazilian federalism in recent years, particularly during Bolsonaro's four years as president, when cooperative federalism, established by the 1988 Federal Constitution and reinforced by various reforms in the following decades, was challenged by the federal government. In the fifth section, we discuss the general analytical framework of the article, explaining the causal mechanisms of institutional transformation and behavioral change among actors within the three institutional pillars and in an integrated manner between them. Finally, in the sixth and final section, we present the conclusions of this work.

II. System of Government

The most evident and profound institutional transformation occurred in the system of government: the gradual strengthening of the National Congress since 2015, with changes in the dynamics of coalition government and the budget increasingly under the control of the legislature, altered the balance of power between the legislature and the executive branch. It is worth mentioning that even before 2015, the legislature had already taken steps to rebalance relations with the executive branch established by the 1988 constitutional model. In 2001, at the end of FHC's term, which was characterized by intensive use of provisional measures, Congress approved a constitutional amendment (EC 32/2001) substantially modifying the procedure for provisional measures, restricting their use by the Executive and increasing the prerogatives of the Legislative. It is true that EC 32/2001 imposed on Congress itself a mechanism for blocking the agenda if a provisional measure is not considered within 45 days, but in 2009, the Speaker of the House, Michel Temer, ruled that the agenda lock would apply only to ordinary bills - by analogy with the legal status of MPs - freeing the legislature to continue enacting constitutional amendments and approving complementary laws, legislative decrees, etc. Temer's interpretation was based on a procedural provision of *the* constitu-

tional *polity*, leading the opposition to file a writ of mandamus with the STF. In a preliminary decision denying the injunction, Justice Celso de Mello stated that “Temer's decision aids in restoring the Legislative Branch's control over its own agenda and reduces the executive Branch's propensity to govern through provisional measures.” (Rennó, 2010). Another change came with Resolution 1/2013-CN, by which Congress imposed on itself the expedited review of presidential vetoes, eliminating internal institutional obstacles to deliberation on them and automating the scheduling of sessions to decide on them - no longer depending on the formation of special committees and the determination of the president of the Senate to do so. This put an end to repeated omissions, which turned presidential vetoes of laws approved by Congress into *fait accompli* (Oliveira, 2014; Pereira, 2024; Rennó & Sassi, 2025).

Although institutional changes had occurred previously, 2015 was a milestone in the redefinition of the foundations of Brazilian presidentialism because it highlighted, at the beginning of President Dilma Rousseff's second term, the loss of congressional support for the head of the executive branch, culminating in her removal from office. Rousseff's difficulties in her relationship with Congress were even the subject of complaints by several deputies in their speeches during the impeachment vote, when they criticized the president's lack of dialogue with legislators³. As will be seen below, our argument about the weakening of the executive branch and the strengthening of Congress focuses on changes in the rules governing relations between the branches of government in the context of coalition presidentialism, especially greater control of the budget by lawmakers and their corresponding lack of interest in controlling ministries. First, however, it is worth highlighting the impact of Operation Car Wash as an external shock that dismantled the coalition supporting Dilma Rousseff, permanently weakening the presidency.

³ Câmara dos Deputados (2016).

In the golden age of coalition presidentialism, the FHC and Lula administrations faced allegations and scandals of corruption, but without the strength to dismantle the coalition and threaten their respective presidential terms. With Operation Car Wash, it was different. The operation set in motion a dynamic that threatened almost the entire Brazilian party system, without Rousseff, intentionally or not, using the tools at her disposal to halt the investigations. It is not necessary to reconstruct the entire process that led to her impeachment (Limongi, 2023), but it is important to highlight for the purposes of our analysis that the impeachment would not have occurred if more than half of the ruling parties had not joined the opposition to promote it. The main reason for the defection was not the fight against corruption or the change in economic policy - the main flags waved in favor of impeachment - but the attempt to take the presidential seat and from there organize the reaction to Operation Car Wash.

In effect, Temer broke Rousseff's isolation and set in motion a plan to regain lost governability. A survey by the newspaper *Valor Econômico*, comparing the presidential agendas of Temer and his predecessor, showed that in 90 days in office, the new president received more members of Congress than Rousseff did in five and a half years (Jubé et al., 2016). However, the plan outlined in a leaked conversation between PMDB members Romero Jucá and Sergio Machado (Em gravação, Jucá..., 2016) did not come to fruition because the arrows of Rodrigo Janot (Jiménez, 2017), then Attorney General, hit Michel Temer and the defeated candidate in the 2014 elections, one of the leaders of the impeachment, PSDB member Aécio Neves.

The Lava Jato investigation, which until then had been conducted from Curitiba, finally reached the upper echelons of the political system, with enough power to disrupt the reaction against the operation below. From then

on, with Temer weakened, it was up to the congressional majority to try to maintain a minimum level of governability in the country until the end of the presidential term, including securing the necessary votes against two complaints filed by the Attorney General's Office to open an investigation against the president. This seems to us to be a turning point in Brazilian presidentialism, when a congressional majority is formed for reasons of survival, submits the presidency to its primary interests, and begins to reform the institutional framework by introducing mechanisms of a new governability from Congress.

Even though Operation Car Wash was interrupted only years later by the intervention of the Supreme Court, the congressional majority forged in Rousseff's impeachment remained united, survived the 2018 elections, and ended up in the legislature contemporary to Bolsonaro's presidency, who abdicated his responsibility to form and lead a coalition (Couto, 2021, 2025). Not surprisingly, this period saw the longest-serving Speaker of the House in the New Republic - Rodrigo Maia, 2016-2021 - and the approval of a series of far-reaching laws and constitutional amendments: the Spending Cap (EC 95/2016), Labor Reform (Law 13467/2017), Pension Reform (EC 103/2019), a "war budget" to tackle the pandemic (EC 106/2020), and a constitutional amendment to pay new emergency aid (EC 109/2021), among others.

In short, Rousseff's unwillingness to engage with Congress (which contributed to her downfall), Temer's fragility (plagued by scandals), and Bolsonaro's abdication of building and leading a coalition (in line with his anti-establishment rhetoric) increasingly weakened the presidency, generating, in return, a congressional majority coordinated by its institutional leaders, which began to define the country's legislative agenda and learned the institutional path to alter the balance of relations between these powers. In this sense, it is worth remembering that the theory of coalition presidentialism has always been based on two foundations (Figueiredo & Limongi, 1999): (i) the legislative and agenda-setting powers of the president and (ii) the centralization of decision-making within Congress, combined with the strong prerogatives of party leaders. It could not be ruled out that the internal arrangement of the legislature also favored parliamentary and party coordination aimed at its own ends and not merely dependent on or associated with the executive branch.

The weakness of the executive branch in Congress has opened the way for the legislature to advance not only in the short term but also structurally, particularly in controlling public resources of interest to it, starting with Constitutional Amendment No. 86, which made "mandatory the implementation of individual amendments by members of Congress to the federal budget (...)", obliging "the government to execute parliamentary amendments to the budget law up to a limit of 1.2% of net current revenue (RCL) realized in the previous year." (Emenda Constitucional 86..., 2015).

This was only the first of a series of regulatory changes regarding legislative power over the budget that shifted the balance of power between the Presidency and Congress in Brazil. In June 2019, the Senate enacted Constitutional Amendment No. 100, making budget amendments by state delegations mandatory as well (Orçamento impositivo para..., 2019). The proposal that gave rise to it was submitted in 2015, the same year that the mandatory nature of individual amendments was approved. Presented at a time when the Presidency was in a fragile state (under Rousseff), the proposal lay dormant for four years until it was finally transformed into constitutional law in a new context, with a president who, for different reasons, was also unable to reach an understanding with Congress. By abdicating his role in building and

leading a congressional coalition, Bolsonaro vacated the space that Congress would have taken in setting the legislative agenda, subverting the unchallenged prevalence of the executive branch in this role - a distinctive feature of Brazilian coalition presidentialism during the New Republic until then (Amorim Neto, 2000; Amorim Neto et al., 2002; Bertholini & Pereira, 2017); McCubbins, 2002; Figueiredo & Limongi, 2007, 1999; Limongi, 2006; Limongi & Figueiredo, 2005, 2017; Neiva, 2011; Pereira & Mueller, 2002; 2003).

Also in 2019, a third constitutional amendment on parliamentary amendments to the federal budget was approved, No. 105. It added another article to the Constitution, allowing “special transfers” to subnational governments (states and municipalities) without the need for an agreement with the federal government, with the only conditions being that the funds must be used in areas within the jurisdiction of the federated entity and that at least 70% of the money must be allocated to capital expenditures - without specifying or requiring accountability. This type of budget amendment became known as the “Pix amendment”⁴, forming part of what daily political jargon dubbed the “secret budget” due to the lack of transparency in the management of resources.

⁴ The name of these amendments, “PIX,” refers to the simplified method of payments and transfers created by the Central Bank of Brazil, which has become very popular. This instrument is explained in detail on the agency’s website (BCB, s.d).

Changes in budgetary rules, with the legislature capturing a significant share of the discretionary budget, have increased the power of Congress at the expense of the executive branch and given the presidents of both houses a leading role in articulating political decisions and driving the decision-making agenda. This change can be measured by the share of the public budget that is now allocated by Congress, without the possibility of blocking or reallocation by the executive branch.

The annual average spending on parliamentary amendments rose from R\$ 20.9 billion between 2017 and 2019 to R\$ 45.4 billion between 2020 and 2022 - a 117% increase. This expansion came not so much from tax amendments or “Pix,” but from another instrument: amendments by the general budget rapporteur. From a legislative expedient used only for minor adjustments to the budget, the rapporteur’s amendments became a rich source of funds that congressmen could direct to their constituencies. From Lula’s first term to Temer’s (2003-2018), the average annual amount of these amendments was R\$ 5.8 billion; with Bolsonaro, it jumped to R\$ 26.2 billion between 2020 and 2022 - a 351% increase (Monteiro, 2022, pp. 33).

Unlike other types of congressional amendments to the budget, those made by the general rapporteur were not mandatory. However, their large volume (which was added to that of other amendments) gave their author immense bargaining power with other legislators. This power allowed him to act as an intermediary for the government in this new form of negotiation, which took on a role similar to that previously reserved for individual and caucus amendments, which became mandatory. Therefore, although the executive branch lost control over the destination of an even larger volume of budgetary funds, which passed to the legislative branch’s decision-making sphere, it used this to bargain for parliamentary support (Valfré & Breno, 2021), and it needed to do so precisely because it had lost bargaining power with Congress, thus resorting to the budget rapporteur and the presidents of the two houses - who were tremendously empowered.

This congressional protagonism was neither ephemeral nor restricted to the presidencies of Bolsonaro and Rousseff, who, for different reasons, related to the legislature in a very different and less successful way than their pre-

decessors. It became institutionally entrenched through changes to the formal rules, becoming the *status quo* for future heads of the executive branch. Even with the Federal Supreme Court (STF) declaring the “secret budget” unconstitutional, Congress remained empowered and in control of a significant portion of the federal government's discretionary budget.

Therefore, the circumstances surrounding the relationship between presidents and Congress have created opportunities for institutional changes that will structurally affect this same relationship in the future. In other words, ***politics transformed polity, which began to guide the functioning of politics and, therefore, policy production in a different way than in the past.*** Couto has called this new dynamic of coalition presidentialism “*congressional government*”⁵, (Couto, 2020b, 2021a, 2023a, 2025). Acir Almeida also used the category of congressional government in a very similar way (Almeida, 2020), adapting the terminology of Colomer & Negretto (2005, pp. 78-87) to the Brazilian case during the Bolsonaro administration. Unlike Almeida, we understand that congressional government was not a dynamic peculiar to the Bolsonaro period, but rather a new, institutionalized form of Brazilian presidentialism.

⁵ “... there was talk of *de facto* parliamentarianism, an inaccurate analogy to describe what a congressional government was. ... the executive branch, unwilling to build a parliamentary base and unable to lead the legislative process, claimed credit for the approval of measures that, although they converged with its economic agenda, were approved more in spite of than thanks to the government” (Couto, 2021a).

The fragility of the executive branch in forming a base in Congress in this new institutional configuration was made explicit by Antonio Rueda, president of the Progressive Union, a right-wing party federation formed in 2025 by União Brasil and Progressistas. In an interview with *Veja* magazine, he said, addressing the relationship between his federation and other pragmatic right-wing parties (Centrão) with the Lula administration:

Our representatives understood that, for the greater good, we should join the base to try to help the country. And so, we did. But it is not because we support policies that we believe are necessary that we are part of the government. (...) It is a fact that the executive branch has been left with reduced political reach. (...) The Ministry of Tourism has a discretionary budget of 30 million reais, which I think is very little for a continental country like ours. (...) With the exception of the PT and PSOL, there is no party that is 100% aligned with the government. You only have to follow the votes to see the lack of unanimity. (...) Today, every member of Congress has a mandatory amendment in the order of 50 to 60 million reais per year. This is not political patronage, but a rule of the game in today's politics (Lima & Ferraz, 2025).

There is a paradox in Rueda's statement: his party is part of the ruling coalition, but it is not part of the government, supporting only agendas that appeal to it. This ambiguity stems from the fact that congressmen have budgetary allocations that exceed those of ministries, as explained in the comparison between the resources of the Ministry of Tourism and the amount of mandatory amendments available to an individual member of Congress. In other words, it is not in the parties' interest to take on the responsibility of being in government, as expressed by occupying ministries, since they can do more with money from mandatory budget amendments. The extent of this financial power of congressmen was made clear in a report pointing out that, among Brazilian municipalities, 44% had a budget lower than the amount of individual amendments made by senators and 14% lower than the amount made by congressmen (Barbon et al., 2025). Thus, “government-aligned-parties” no longer had a reason to align as before.

This fact, however, is not surprising in light of theory. According to Bard & Mair (2010), the party system is forged from limitations and opportunities that affect all parties equally, even though they may trigger different strategies for action. The authors analyze the three main types of divisions that determine

the formation of party systems: vertical (cleavages within society), horizontal (electoral competition at different levels of government - national, regional, and local), and functional (electoral, parliamentary, and governmental arenas). The latter, in particular, explains how it is possible for parties to form a parliamentary coalition that includes, but is not limited to, support for the government, without this translating into the occupation of positions and control of resources through ministerial portfolios in the government. This seems to be the current trend in the Brazilian party system.

However, this radically changes the functioning of coalition presidentialism, as it weakens alliances and consolidates the logic of congressional government, despite the negotiating efforts of the executive branch and the coalescent sharing of ministries (in proportion to the size of the legislative benches) (Amorim Neto, 2000; Amorim Neto et al., 2002) or even the ideological affinity between the president and the parties with which he or she *seeks to ally* (Bertholini & Pereira, 2017).

In addition to changes in budgetary rules, with direct effects on the decision-making process, there have been significant changes in the organization of the electoral and party systems - with inevitable repercussions on the system of government, since the characteristics of the party system condition the formation and management of coalitions. Changes in electoral and party rules, together with changes in electoral financing, have reduced the number of parties and deepened the *cartelization* of the system (Katz & Mair, 1995).

After decades of criticism of excessive multipartyism and party fragmentation in Brazil, reforms were finally implemented, largely triggered by court decisions (Herzog, 2025; Marchetti, 2015; Marchetti & Cortez, 2009): party loyalty, prohibition of corporate donations and electoral coalitions in proportional elections, and the establishment of a performance clause. The path has been erratic, with comings and goings marked by forceful interventions by the judiciary (TSE and STF) in the contexts of the 'Mensalão' scandal (when the TSE established party loyalty) and Operation Car Wash (when the STF decided to abolish corporate campaign donations), but not without reactions from Congress in all cases.

An analysis of the sequence of reforms suggests that a cartelization of the party system may be underway: with the end of corporate donations, parties reacted by creating a billion-dollar electoral fund, increasing their dependence on public resources (a characteristic of cartelization). Concerned about how the pie will be divided, the parties that approved the new Special Campaign Financing Fund (FEFC) allocated only 2% of the resources for equal distribution among all parties registered with the TSE, and 98% proportionally among those that hold seats in Congress. This distribution rule effectively freezes the party landscape, making it extremely difficult for small parties to grow and new ones to emerge.

Two other measures to close the electoral and party market were (1) the end of the possibility of coalitions in proportional elections and (2) the performance clause, conditioning access to resources on obtaining a minimum percentage of votes in a minimum number of states. In a short period of time, these measures had a strong impact, reducing the number of parties with representation in the Chamber of Deputies by one-third, from 30 in 2018 to 20 in 2025 (if we consider party federations as parties, the number drops to 16 - almost half of the initial number). The decrease is equally significant in the effective number of parties: from 16.5 in 2018 to 9.3 in 2025 - a 44% drop.

Even though streamlining of the party system may benefit presidents interested in forging and leading coalition governments, as it simplifies the coordination of allies, the combination of the new form of electoral financing with greater budgetary control by Congress gives the parties greater autonomy *vis-à-vis* the executive branch. Although the theory of coalition presidentialism places great emphasis on the role of the executive branch in coordinating the legislative agenda, albeit through representatives, the reduction in the number of parties in the context of the changes outlined above may help Congress to coordinate.

Empirical evidence of the benefits of this situation concerns voters on the other side of the equation: nine out of ten votes for the Chamber of Deputies in 2022 were valid, meaning that only one was wasted. In 20 of the 27 federal units, the sum of null and blank votes was lower for federal deputies than for governors in 2022, indicating high levels of voter mobilization and vote utilization by parties in the fierce contest for a seat in parliament. We do not know what came first, whether it was the increase in party control over public resources (budgetary and FEFC) or the increase in the value of the voter's vote, but certainly both go hand in hand today.

A relationship is therefore established between political actors and institutional structures in which certain courses of action by certain agents create opportunities for others to change the institutional structure in their favor; the dynamics of the game allow the rules of the game to be changed. Subsequently, these same actors interact according to the new institutional structure and thus act differently from their predecessors, as the available strategies for action have changed. Such institutional change is not neutral, as it permanently affects the balance of power between the Presidency and Congress. It is important to emphasize that opportunities for change in *polity* were created, but they were not inevitable. In other words, the *necessary* conditions for change existed, but *they were insufficient*. Decisions by the actors involved in *politics* on both sides were decisive in ensuring that the opportunities were translated into changes in *polity*.

Figure 1 summarizes the elements of the analysis of what happened within the government system.

III. Justice system

In the case of the justice system, important formal changes to the institutional structure largely predate the period analyzed here, due to the institutional framework established in 1988 with the new Constitution (Arantes, 1997, 1999, 2002, 2007; Arantes & Kerche, 1999; Kerche, 2007; Koerner & Freitas, 2013) and modified in 2004 through the comprehensive reform approved in 2004 through Constitutional Amendment 45.

This reform actually began in 1992 with Constitutional Amendment Proposal (PEC) 96, presented by Deputy Hélio Bicudo (PT). After 12 years of debate, passing through several rapporteurs and taking on various versions, the PEC was finally approved, bringing innovations that increased the powers of the Federal Supreme Court, among which it is worth highlighting the creation of Binding Precedents and General Repercussion, mechanisms that reinforced the STF's constitutional control power, conforming to what Oscar Vilhena Vieira called "supremocracy" (Vieira, 2008).

Figure 1 - Actors, institutions, and processes within the government system

Source: prepared by the authors, 2025.

The institutional strengthening of the court at *polity* level affected not only external *politics* but also internal *politics* within the court. Until then, the renewal of the court's composition promoted by presidential appointments, including those made by Lula, was not reflected in significant changes in the judicial behavior of the ministers or in marked divisions within the court. but Desposato and his colleagues (Desposato et al., 2014) have shown that the increase in the STF's authority with EC 45 seems to have stimulated more incisive action by the ministers, including in ideological terms (in the sense of the attitudinal model of *judicial politics*), also resulting in the emergence of unprecedented divisions among them. Such assertiveness and intensification were linked to the individual powers available to STF members (prerogatives of the rapporteur, the possibility of interrupting trials by requesting a review, monocratic decisions, etc.), leading the literature to shift from "supremocracy," that is, the powers of the STF as a court, to "ministerocracy," i.e., the individual powers of its ministers (Arguelhes & Ribeiro, 2018).

Last but not least, even the idea of establishing external control of the judiciary ended up taking the form of the National Council of Justice, which is subject to the STF in the constitutional hierarchy of judicial bodies and whose composition is mostly endogenous to the judiciary. For no other reason, the CNJ ended up becoming the administrative arm of the judiciary itself, through which the judiciary drafts and implements public policies on justice (Arantes, 2015), largely in response to the effects caused by its own interventions in government policies. The case of the institutional arrangement developed by the CNJ to deal with the judicialization of health and its effects is emblematic in this regard (Tulii, 2018).

It was in this context of strengthening the STF that most of the changes to the electoral and party rules, highlighted in the previous section, were introduced on the initiative of the court or through decisions taken by the TSE and upheld by the Supreme Court. The creation of the party loyalty rule took place against the backdrop of the 'Mensalão' scandal and can be seen as an attempt

by the justices who formed majorities in both courts to discipline the functioning of the party system, removing from the game the currency of party exchanges used to forge government coalitions. The decision to ban corporate donations to election campaigns took place in the context of Operation Car Wash, although Minister Gilmar Mendes retained a request for review so that the rule would only apply after the 2014 elections. The court had already formed a majority in 2013 to end corporate donations, but Mendes considered that the PT had already raised funds by that point and that the opposition should be given a chance to do the same. The strategy did not work, Rousseff was re-elected - albeit by a narrow margin - but the election produced evidence of corporate donations that was later used in Operation Car Wash to extract confessions from contractors against government parties, but also against the opposition. After the election, in 2015, the minister returned the case to the plenary, which concluded the vote to end corporate donations.

Under the presidency of Eduardo Cunha, the Chamber of Deputies attempted to reinstate these donations through legislation, but Dilma Rousseff upheld the Supreme Court's decision and vetoed corporate campaign financing. It is beyond the scope of this article to detail the interactions between the judiciary (TSE and STF) and the legislature that led to the rule changes and, in turn, to the transformation of the party system. but it is noteworthy how they were introduced through successive rounds involving judicial decisions and legislative responses until they were finally enshrined in the constitutional text, especially through amendments 97/2017 and 111/2021. In this case, therefore, external shocks (corruption scandals and judicial interventions) led to successive rounds of interaction between the branches of government and changes in the rules of the electoral and party game, culminating in the elevation of these norms to the constitutional level - that is, *politics* led to the redefinition of *polity*.

Over the years, a proactive Supreme Court in adjudicating issues related to the legislature and the individualistic activism of some of its magistrates have supported those who see excesses in the court's actions. Analysts concerned with the defense of democracy and the risk of conflicts between the branches of government have been pointing out these problems for several years (Arguelhes & Ribeiro, 2018; Glezer & Vieira, 2024; Vieira, 2008; Vieira et al., 2022), noting the intense activity of the Judiciary and the Public Prosecutor's Office in the political sphere, judicial activism, the judicialization of politics, and the politicization of justice (Arguelhes et al., 2016; Barboza & Kozicki, 2012; Carvalho & Leitão, 2010; Couto & Oliveira, 2019; Marchetti & Cortez, 2009; Oliveira, 2005; Recondo & Weber, 2019; Vianna et al., 2007).

These criticisms of the STF's functioning received an institutional response from the court at the end of 2022, through Regimental Amendment No. 58 (STF, 2022). In it, the court reformed itself, establishing two important measures: (1) that monocratic decisions by its members should be immediately submitted to collegiate review; (2) that requests for review would have a maximum period of 90 days, after which they would be automatically submitted to a vote (STF, 2022). With this initiative by the then president of the court, Rosa Weber, the Supreme Court demonstrated some sense of self-restraint and sought to put an end to practices that, while empowering individual ministers, undermined the collegial functioning and legitimacy of the court itself - something especially relevant in a context of fierce attacks on the STF by a populist president.

More central to the concerns of this article are the behavioral changes of judicial actors that occurred after 2012, with the judgment of Criminal Action

470 ('Mensalão'). The STF, in addition to its important role as the body responsible for the concentrated control of the constitutionality of legal norms, thanks to the 'Mensalão' judgment, established the special jurisdiction for high-ranking officials. Until then, this was an area where politicians under judicial scrutiny found refuge, with little chance of punishment (Taylor & Buranelli, 2007). Although the case ended as a "crime without a perpetrator" (Arantes, 2018) and the thesis of the formation of a gang to undermine democracy was not confirmed in court, significant convictions were achieved, teaching the political class that this forum was no longer as privileged as previously imagined. From then on, the STF also gained prominence as a judge in the criminal sphere, not only in cases involving corruption of public officials, but also of other kinds (Armani, 2023; Falcão & Oliveira, 2013; Fontainha & Lima, 2020).

On the one hand, this greater prominence was largely due to the perception among judicial actors that new courses of action were possible, allowing for more incisive control of the political class through criminal proceedings to combat corruption (Arantes, 2011a, 2011b). On the other hand, there were also institutional reasons: Law 12.850/2013, which established plea bargaining and other investigative tools that significantly strengthened the work of the police and the Public Prosecutor's Office. For now, for the purposes of this discussion, it suffices to note that Operation Car Wash would have been unthinkable without such legislation (Bottino, 2016) and without the institutional affirmation of control bodies such as the Public Prosecutor's Office and the Federal Police behind the judicial escalation against the political class (Arantes, 2015, 2011a, 2019, 2021). Lava Jato is the result of this process, which combined institutional development and strategic action by legal operators (Marona & Kerche, 2021; Rodrigues, 2020). Its impact, however, was devastating on Brazilian politics, affecting electoral competition and reinforcing anti-establishment and anti-political sentiment in society, thus contributing to the emergence of outsiders and the far right (Avritzer, 2020; Couto, 2018; Lynch & Cassimiro, 2022).

In fact, the 'Mensalão' trial and Operation Car Wash contributed to shaking up national politics, undermining trust in professional politicians, parties, and representative institutions in general. However, with the election of Jair Bolsonaro and the arrival of the far right in the federal government (Couto, 2020a), the Federal Supreme Court (and, subsidiarily, the Superior Electoral Court) began to act as a dam against attacks on democracy. The same court that had approved Lula's imprisonment ordered his release about a year and a half later, motivated by the revelations of *Vaza Jato* (Car Wash Leaks), which brought to light the methods used by the judge and prosecutors in Curitiba. In effect, the court's course correction significantly increased hatred of the court by those who publicly defended that "the Supreme Court is the people"; however, whether intentional or not, the fact is that it brought back to the political scene one of the few leaders capable of confronting Bolsonaro in his attempt at reelection. And as Levitsky & Ziblatt (2018) point out, the greatest risk to democracy is not in the first election of an authoritarian leader, but in the second, which confirms him.

It is a fact that the Bolsonaro administration had a president who was less concerned with advancing a public policy agenda than with constantly stirring up his social base through *live broadcasts* and public appearances, constituting what Couto calls a *movement-government* (Couto, 2021b, 2023b; Couto & Abrucio, 2025). This continuous process of agitation was compounded by repeated violations of the legal system, mainly through decrees, ordinances, and other administrative measures, characterizing what Vilhena Vieira and

partners define as *authoritarian infralegalism* (Vieira et al., 2022). This prompted a reaction from social and political-institutional actors, who appealed to the Judiciary in an attempt to stop the president and his aides. Such action became even more necessary in the face of an ineffective Attorney General's Office (PGR), which had been converted into an auxiliary force of the Executive with the appointment of a prosecutor aligned with Bolsonaro and subservient to him, eager for his reappointment and even a nomination to the Supreme Court (Marona & Kerche, 2021). When Bolsonarism began to attack democratic institutions through massive disinformation and fake news campaigns, as well as encouraging large-scale anti-democratic acts targeting the STF, the court opened the first investigations that placed Bolsonaro and his allies in the criminal crosshairs of the Court, from which they never emerged, culminating in the trial of the former president and several of his military and civilian allies for attempted *coup d'état*.

Partly on its own initiative, filling the void left by the Attorney General's Office, and partly driven by actions from society and the political system, the Supreme Court began to act as a veto player, imposing checks and balances on the autocratic initiatives of the Executive Branch (Lijphart, 2012; Tsebelis, 2000, 2002). Along these lines, Vieira et al. (2022) show how the consensual nature of the Brazilian political system was important in containing Bolsonaro, and Melo & Pereira (2024) use the same idea to argue why democracy did not die in Brazil.

However, as we have seen, the path has not been linear, and this has thrown the Supreme Court into a *populist trap* (Couto, 2023a, 2023b), which can be described as follows: by repeatedly transgressing the law, the executive branch triggers the activation of the judiciary; which in turn causes the Executive to react by attacking the Judiciary, accusing it of illegitimately preventing the government (the “true” representative of the “people”) from functioning; such attacks produce an institutional counter-reaction from the Judiciary, which defends itself by repelling the Executive's attack; in the face of such defense, the Executive raises the tone even further, accusing the Judiciary of taking sides against it and, therefore, of behaving as a partisan and anti-popular actor, violating the impartiality that should characterize it; this dynamic, despite the support of the president's opponents for the judiciary's actions, undermines confidence in justice and reduces its legitimacy in the eyes of other segments of society. A Datafolha poll showed that, in September 2021, the proportion of those who said they “trusted a lot” in the Judiciary was the lowest since April 2017, while those who said they “did not trust” it was the highest (Datafolha: Cai confiança..., 2021). This was a recurring theme during the four years of the Bolsonaro administration and even after its end.

In short, the emergence of the populist far right and its attacks on democracy led the judiciary to take on a new role in this context: that of the main bastion in defense of the democratic rule of law. With the attacks of January 8, 2023 (which destroyed the headquarters of the three branches of government) and the revelation that a coup had been orchestrated by those defeated in the 2022 election, the STF clearly took on the task of holding the leaders of the coup attempt politically and criminally responsible, while the TSE made Bolsonaro ineligible in the first of the lawsuits filed against the former president.

Furthermore, it is worth noting that the Supreme Court also played a key role, in the context of the Covid-19 pandemic and in other situations, in protecting not only the institutional structure, as in the case of the decree abolishing participatory councils in the federal administration, but also public policies that were under attack by the extremist government. An example of this was

the defense of scientifically based health measures, as well as environmental and social policies (Couto & Abrucio, 2025).

After Lula took office in 2023, the STF and TSE began to deal with the consequences of Bolsonaro anti-democratic actions as president. Even with the specter of amnesty for coup plotters haunting the court's work, the acceptance of the complaint filed by the Attorney General and the pace of the criminal investigation indicated the Court's determination to investigate and punish those who attempted to undermine democracy. And while leading a coalition government in Congress proved to be an inglorious task for Lula III, the president now has the Supreme Federal Court as an ally. In addition to conducting criminal proceedings against his main opponents or executors, the court ruled in favor of the executive branch on fiscal and tax issues, also punishing Congress's opaque control over the federal budget through decisions by Minister Flávio Dino (appointed by Lula) that impose transparency and traceability in the execution of parliamentary amendments.

Although winding and oscillating, the path taken by the STF in recent decades shows how it is a court absorbed by the political system (Dahl, 1957), with decisions that affect and are affected by the correlation of forces. If today the court is once again advancing in its institutional affirmation, without fear of major retaliation, the eventual election of a new populist government in the future and/or an adverse majority in the Senate will put even greater pressure on it. Will the court be able to once again play the role of a bulwark against authoritarianism? Without attempting to predict the future, this question serves as a guide for assessing the consequences of the role played by the judiciary's leadership at this critical juncture, as well as its eventual consolidation beyond the current context, establishing a structural element of Brazilian democratic institutionality.

Figure 2 summarizes the elements of the analysis of what happened within the justice system.

Figure 2 - Actors, institutions, and processes within the justice system

Source: prepared by the authors, 2025.

IV. Federalism

The federal structure was also affected during this period of successive crises. The 1988 Constitution established a model of cooperative federalism based on public policy systems and intergovernmental partnerships, with a predominance of coordination between the federal government and municipalities (Arretche, 2012; Bichir et al., 2020; Franzese & Abrucio, 2013). This model is characterized by sectoral heterogeneities, with some areas of cooperation more developed, such as the Unified Health System (SUS), whose institutionalization has gradually consolidated since 1988, and others in a precarious state, such as the Unified Public Security System (SUSP), created only in 2018, which is poorly institutionalized and has only formal governance. Despite this, cooperative coordination has been continuously strengthened over almost thirty years (Abrucio et al., 2023; Silva et al., 2023), benefiting from the incremental strategy of different governments, which were more committed to consolidating, improving, and expanding inherited policies than to completely modifying or dismantling them (as Bolsonaro attempted to do).

However, since Michel Temer's brief presidency, and especially during Jair Bolsonaro's administration, Brazilian cooperative federalism has not emerged unscathed from the crisis that has also affected the other institutional pillars erected since redemocratization. A less cooperative dynamic, and later, with Bolsonarism, one of open confrontation, has established itself between the federal government and the subnational entities of the Brazilian tripartite federation (in which municipalities are also autonomous federal entities) (Campez, 2019; Zraick, 2021). This became more evident during the Covid-19 pandemic, but had already been occurring since 2019, with repeated clashes between the president and state governors (Abrucio et al., 2020). This occurred in the clash over fuel prices⁶, the lack of dialogue with state secretaries of education⁷, the president's verbal attacks on governors of the Northeast⁸, the dismantling of the municipal arm of the Unified Social Assistance System (SUAS)⁹, among other conflictual contexts (Abrucio, 2021).

The confrontation over fuel prices and state taxes on them provides a paradigmatic example of this confrontational federalism embraced by Bolsonarism in government. In late 2019 and early 2020, the president began to blame state governments for high prices at the pump, demanding that states reduce the ICMS tax rate on fuel and even proposing to change the law to compel state governments to lower taxation.

The main dispute in the federal arena, however, occurred during the pandemic, as the federal government attempted to impose its health policy preferences on subnational entities - contrary to the recommendations of the World Health Organization (WHO) and the overwhelming majority of the scientific community. As noted in the previous section of this article, the STF played a crucial role in this case by declaring Provisional Measure 926/2020 unconstitutional¹⁰, safeguarding the concurrent powers of states and municipalities to adopt health measures. This exacerbated the president's animosity toward the court (Vieira, 2020), who, in a disinformation campaign, adopted the narrative that the STF had tied his hands, when in fact the Court's action was intended to free state entities from obstacles to implementing necessary measures against the pandemic.

This unsuccessful attempt to override the autonomy of subnational entities stemmed from the president and his government's conception of how intergovernmental relations should be. While Bolsonaro proclaimed his desire for

⁶ Bolsonaro quer nova lei para forçar Estados a baixar ICMS sobre gasolina (2020).

Poder360; Bolsonaro sugere compensar alta do petróleo com redução de ICMS. (2020).

Correio Braziliense;

Bolsonaro desafia governadores e diz que zera impostos sobre combustível se eles zerarem o ICMS (2020) *O Globo*.

⁷ "MEC não tem comando", diz conselho de Estados. (2019) *Valor Econômico*. 27 mar.

⁸ Bolsonaro diz que fala sobre governadores de 'paraíba' foi crítica a Dino e Azevêdo (2019) *GI*.

⁹ Prefeitos reclamam da falta de repasse regular dos recursos da assistência social. *CNM* (2019) 28 fev.

¹⁰ Ministro assegura que estados, DF e municípios podem adotar medidas contra pandemia (2020a) *STF*. STF reconhece competência concorrente de estados, DF, municípios e União no combate à Covid-19 (2020b) *STF*.

“Less Brasília, More Brazil”, delegating many of the federal government's obligations to state and municipal governments and absolving himself of responsibility, he attempted to impose his own agenda on them, in a logic of power concentration consistent with his authoritarianism. Abrucio and his colleagues called this peculiar and contradictory concept “Bolsonarist federalism” (Abrucio et al., 2020), a model based on confrontation with federal actors, in contrast to the cooperative federalism proposed in 1988, which functioned more fully between 1993 and 2014.

The fact is that Brazilian federalism, through the actions of subnational governments and the arbitration of the STF, played a crucial role in containing the Bolsonaro government's authoritarian advances. In this case, there were no formal institutional changes (not least because Bolsonaro's federalism project failed), but the capacity for resistance and resilience of institutions was evident, as they stood up to the attacks launched by the federal government and thus acted as a bulwark against the authoritarian project.

Even without structural changes to the federal institutional framework, the actions of subnational governments in opposition to the federal government's denialism during the pandemic were important, as they provided opportunities for *institutional learning*, reinforcing political actors' perception of their effective power in the federal system. Governors played a leading role in promoting health policies capable of compensating for the federal government's inaction (or even sabotage). This leadership was clear in the São Paulo state government's support for the development of a vaccine by the Butantan Institute, as well as in the coordination of northeastern governors through the Northeast Consortium, an entity that was strengthened during this critical period.

The same phenomenon of the federal government's coordination role being undermined occurred in the field of education policy, when the Council of State Education Secretaries (Consed) and the National Union of Municipal Education Directors (Undime) set the school calendar in the face of the Ministry of Education's inaction, as well as in climate policy, where interstate consortia were set up to deal with the issue, in contrast to the denialism of Bolsonaro's environmental policy. Thus, subnational *politics* had the dual role of ensuring *policies* and defending *polity*.

This had consequences beyond the four years of Jair Bolsonaro's presidency, allowing state governments to continue to coordinate. It is no coincidence that Lula's government began with the new president engaging in more direct dialogue with state governments, seeking to reestablish the dialogue that had been interrupted during his predecessor's term. Illustrative of the continuity of this interaction in the new government is the direct dialogue between the Presidency and governors on public security policy - despite resistance from some far-right state leaders to federal initiatives. Another example is the creation of a national literacy pact, in which the federal government works with states and municipalities (Abrucio & Marques, 2025).

Cooperative federalism remains an appropriate model for producing public policies in a federation that combines great territorial inequality and local state capacities with strong decentralization of public service provision (Grin & Abrucio, 2019). However, the destruction of some federal policies and capacities during the Temer and, above all, Bolsonaro administrations, as well as the need for subnational governments to react to the federal government's inaction by building collective responses on their own, has created a new intertwining between *polity*, *politics*, and *policy*. The consequence of this process, given the risk of paralysis or the creation of obstacles to federal partner-

ships, is the need for the federal government to share more power with states and municipalities or, at least, engage in deeper dialogue with them to convince them in the intergovernmental game. The new dynamics of federal relations support the argument for strengthening Congress as the locus where relations between the Union, states, and municipalities are often negotiated, considerably reducing presidential authority on this *front* as well. In short, to remain operational, cooperative federalism can no longer be the same as it was in the immediate post-1988 period.

Figure 3 summarizes the elements of the analysis of what happened in the context of federalism.

V. Discussion

The description of the processes involving each of the three institutional pillars allowed us to observe structural (institutional) and conjunctural (behavioral) changes in the functioning of each of the spheres and, above all, in the interaction between them, as well as the resilience of institutions to the stress produced by the transgressions and attacks promoted by Bolsonarism.

Structural changes were evident in the system of government, with the establishment of new constitutional norms relating to budgetary policy, permanently empowering the legislative branch and consolidating congressional government. The root causes of these processes were crises in relations between the executive and legislative branches, caused by the (in)action of presidents who, due to an unwillingness to compromise (Rousseff) or abdication (Bolsonaro), failed to act within the coalition presidential system in accordance with the institutional requirements of that system of government. This requires presidents to play a diligent role as coalition leaders, coordinating them and cultivating dialogue with parliamentarians in general and party leaders in particular. Equally significant were the two major corruption scan-

Figure 3 - Actors, institutions, and processes in the context of federalism

Source: prepared by the authors, 2025.

dals - Mensalão and Lava Jato - caused by the actions of oversight bodies, which destabilized the functioning of governing coalitions centered on incentives inherent to coalition presidentialism. While the first did not result in the collapse of the government, the second opened the door to the second presidential impeachment in the new Republic and the emergence of an anti-system political movement.

The activities that acted as causal mechanisms for the transformations in the system of government were, first, the failure of presidents (albeit for different reasons) to meet the institutional requirements of relations between the executive and legislative branches; second, the consequent advance of party leaders and Congress into the unoccupied political space, mobilizing the dissatisfaction of their peers to modify budgetary rules, both with Rousseff (in 2015, EC 86) and with Bolsonaro (in 2019, ECs 100 and 105). In other words, the root cause of institutional change - the crises in relations between the branches of government - did not arise by chance, but from the actions of specific entities (presidents and congressional leaders), aggravated by external pressures from the actions of oversight bodies: *politics* determined the change in *polity*.

In the justice system, it is possible to identify behavioral changes among actors, with new strategies for action within the existing institutional framework, while judicial decisions aimed at transforming rules of *polity* have also become increasingly frequent in the context of major corruption scandals. As we have seen, the Mensalão scandal paved the way for judicial activism on two fronts: in the reform of electoral and party rules - such as the institution of party loyalty by judicial determination - and in the handling of special jurisdiction by prerogative of function as an arena in which the STF exercises control over the political class (and whose boundaries the Court itself updates from time to time, redefining who remains and who leaves its sights).

The Operation Lava Jato (Car Wash) represented a greater challenge to the STF, in that it began and took place for the most part in the lower court in Curitiba, to the point that the court endorsed the operation in its early stages and then, for the reasons mentioned above, declared it bankrupt and reversed it almost entirely. In between, the STF banned corporate campaign donations, a measure that led the political class to a profound restructuring of campaign financing and the Brazilian electoral and party systems, triggering the process of cartelization that we have described, involving the end of coalitions and the adoption of the performance clause. Although we speak of the judiciary's leading role, the changes in *polity* that have achieved constitutional status also reflect the reactions of Congress, even if they represent a rush forward in the face of judicial decisions. On the other hand, it is worth noting that the STF, beset by criticism of what was seen as excessive protagonism on the part of the court, took initiatives of self-restraint and self-reform, such as those aimed at strengthening collegiality and reducing "monocratism."

Subsequently, with the Supreme Court already in this prominent position, attacks on democracy (including on the court itself) by the far right ensued, prompting a reaction. These attacks were the primary cause of this second stage of transformation. The activities that operated as causal mechanisms were investigations opened by the STF to deal with this situation (fake news, anti-democratic acts, *coup d'état*), as well as the legal proceedings that arose from them. The PGR, then aligned with Bolsonaro (Augusto Aras), was a relevant entity in this context in a peculiar way: as a passive actor, its omission served as a stimulus for the activism of the STF and one of its ministers in particular, Alexandre de Moraes, who anchored himself in the work of a Federal

Police team, also lending him protection against the then president's attacks on the corporation.

Consequently, the same type of mechanism can be seen in the justice system with the omission of the Attorney General and, in the context of the government system, with the unwillingness to negotiate or with presidential abdication. In both situations, when an entity fails to perform the role required by the institutional structure, space opens up for other entities to advance in the same field - the STF in the justice system (with exceptional support from the PF, bypassing the PGR) and Congress in the system of government (advancing on the weakened presidency). In the case of the system of government, presidential behavior led to *institutional change*; in the justice system, the *behavioral* change of judges was fundamental to ensuring democratic *resilience*. In both situations, *politics* affected *polity*, either by transforming it or preserving it.

In the case of the third pillar, federalism, the transformation was predominantly behavioral and institutional learning (rather than formal changes), characterizing *institutional resilience*. The main cause were disagreements over intergovernmental relations in the field of public policy, particularly in combating the pandemic. Faced with the difficulties imposed by the populist federal executive in these conflicts, subnational governments had to adopt adaptation strategies that would allow them to fulfill their governmental responsibilities, implement public policies, and preserve federal autonomy.

During the pandemic, this was evidenced by the need for state governors to circumvent the federal executive branch in determining health measures and acquiring hospital equipment and supplies. Examples of actions in opposition to the presidency were the purchase of ventilators by the Northeast Consortium and the encouragement of vaccine production by the São Paulo state government. The STF's decision, safeguarding the health powers of subnational governments in the face of the presidential attempt to restrict them, shows that the Supreme Court was also a crucial entity in this area. This adaptation by subnational governments in such a difficult context fostered resilience and produced lessons that may influence future actions. And, for the record, the experience also highlighted the importance of the resilience of public policy systems - albeit with significant variations between them, as demonstrated, for example, by the strength of the SUS on the one hand and the fragility of the environmental area on the other. Here, the dispute over *policy* affected *politics*, resulting in the preservation of *the federal polity*.

The following table (Table 1) summarizes the analysis.

Figure 4 summarizes the main elements presented in the Analytical Table that structure the general analysis of institutional change and resilience in Brazilian democracy in the period 2012-2025.

VI. Conclusion

In this article, we discuss the transformations and resilience of Brazilian democratic institutions, especially between 2012 and 2025. The analysis was structured around three central pillars: the multiparty presidential system of government, the justice system, and federalism. We addressed the institutional changes and challenges faced within each of these pillars, highlighting the complex and interdependent relationship between politics, institutions, and

Table 1 - Analytical framework: process tracing of political changes and democratic resilience

Institutional pillar	Change or resilience (effect/result)	Root causes	Entities (actors and institutions)	Causal mechanisms	Activities
System of Government	Change: Gain of congressional control over the budget (institutional/polity)	Relationship crises between the executive and legislative branches and major corruption scandals	Presidents without parliamentary support (Rousseff and Bolsonaro); party and congressional leaders; control bodies	Unwillingness to negotiate with the legislature and poor coalition management (Rousseff). Rejection of coalition building and abdication (Bolsonaro) Actions by oversight bodies and, in response, coordination of Rousseff's impeachment as a reaction to Operation Car Wash	
	Change: Congressional government (institutional/polity)		Presidents of the Houses of Congress, budget rapporteur, party leaders	Amendment of constitutional rules on budget amendments, empowering Congress	
Justice System	Change: Increased prominence of the Supreme Federal Court (behavioral/politics and constitutional/polity)	2004 Constitutional Reform. Corruption scandals (Mensalão and Lava Jato)	Supreme Federal Court, Attorney General's Office, and oversight bodies	Mensalão trial in the STF; Interventions by the STF and TSE in electoral and party rules. STF's role in Lava Jato	
	Resilience: Role in containing authoritarianism (behavioral/politics)	Attacks on democracy by populist leaders and activists	Supreme Federal Court; PGR (passive actor); PF (investigative arm)	Judicial response to attacks: investigations into fake news, anti-democratic acts, coup attempts, and related proceedings	
	Change: Regulatory Amendment 58/2022 (institutional/polity)	Questioning of the legitimacy of the STF due to the exacerbated individualism of its members	Critics: the political class in general, the press, academia. President of the STF (Rosa Weber)	Institutional reform of the functioning of the STF to minimize individualism	
Federalism	Resilience: Adaptation, alternative policies, institutional learning (behavioral/politics/policy)	Pandemic, fuel costs, education policy, response to climate change	Governors, Federal Executive, Supreme Court, municipalities, interstate consortia	Federal government abdication of responsibility for social policies. Conflict over pandemic management, conflict over fuel taxation, regulation of basic education, climate policy	

Source: prepared by the authors, 2025.

Figure 4 - Institutional change and resilience of Brazilian democracy (2012-2025)

Source: prepared by the authors, 2025.

public policies (*politics, polity, and policy*), through which each of these dimensions has transformed the others in different contexts.

Our intention was, first, to contribute to a deeper understanding of the vicissitudes of Brazilian democracy since 2012. Second, the analysis presented here offers insights for the study of other cases of democratic regimes in which similar phenomena occur, since the adaptability and resilience of the Brazilian institutions serve as a reference for understanding other polyarchies facing similar challenges, with their democratic institutions under stress due to the actions of illiberal rulers. The Brazilian experience shows that, despite many problems, the democracy of this country has lessons to teach. The Brazilian experience is not just a case study, but a laboratory for rethinking the relationship between institutions and democracy in contexts of polarization and uncertainty.

In the case analyzed here, institutional changes - whether formal or resulting from learning on the part of actors - arose from political actors' responses to crises and the opportunities they presented, redefining power balances and forms of governance. The resilience of Brazilian democratic institutions was evidenced by their adaptability and resistance to challenges, even in contexts of deep crisis and with powerful actors clearly motivated to break the democratic institutional framework. It is clear that democratic resilience in Brazil has depended on the joint (though not always coordinated) action of different institutional actors, including the legislature, the judiciary, and subnational governments.

The effort to safeguard the democratic regime in the face of a set of endogenous and exogenous factors that have shaken the political system over the last decade has left indelible marks on the democratic polity designed in 1988, which will continue to challenge the country's political governability.

The first of these is the strengthening of the National Congress, especially through budgetary control (tax amendments and "secret budgets"), which has structurally altered the balance of power between the executive and legislative branches, calling into question the future of the country's system of government. What was once a presidential system with a predominant executive branch has been transformed into a *congressional government*, in which the legislature has gained lasting prominence and the centralization of parliamen-

tary dynamics that once served the interests of the president now contributes to Congress governing itself. Although resulting from adverse political circumstances and presidents who failed to control their coalitions or abdicated them (Rousseff and Bolsonaro), this phenomenon has lasting effects, as it has led to institutional changes that will shape future governance strategies.

In addition, the STF emerged as a central actor in the defense of democracy during the Bolsonaro administration, after contributing to the destabilization of the political system that allowed him to rise to power. This type of judicial protagonism has brought with it challenges, such as the erosion of the judiciary's legitimacy through the *populist trap*, in which the court's response to corruption scandals or its reaction to transgressions committed by the executive branch has fueled narratives of politicization and partisanship in the justice system. The question remains: to what extent is this preeminence sustainable in a democratic context, and how can judicial protagonism be reconciled with accountability *and* self-restraint? One sign that the future seems open and uncertain is the growing volume of legislative proposals aimed at reforming the Supreme Court, from the appointment of its ministers to the compliance of its decisions, including the rules governing its internal functioning.

Finally, cooperative federalism was challenged by the open confrontation between the federal government and subnational entities before and during the pandemic, revealing both weaknesses (such as the lack of coordination in educational and environmental policies, for example) and resilient capacities (such as the articulation of the Northeast Consortium and the ability of the SUS to resist Bolsonaro's denialism). Recent experience suggests that Brazilian federalism guarantees safeguards for subnational autonomy (Abrucio et al., 2023), which can be an antidote to authoritarian centralism, but also exposes the need for more robust mechanisms of intergovernmental cooperation, as subnational governments will seek greater protagonism in federal coordination processes, without, however, the federal government losing its redistributive role.

In summary, it can be concluded that, from now on, it will be necessary to rebuild relations and dialogue between the Union, states, and municipalities in order to ensure the functioning of a new cooperative federalism, strengthening coordination in sectors where it did not exist (such as public security and the environment) and creating new paths for coordination in the social area, giving greater prominence to state governments. The federal government will have to share more power, but it will be essential to avoid coordination between entities (and within policies), as well as to reduce territorial inequalities. In addition, new challenges are emerging for federalism, such as the agenda for collaborative and multilevel governance, as is clear in areas that require greater intersectorality, such as early childhood and climate change.

The originality and main contribution of this work to the comparative study of democracies in a context of destabilization lies in interpreting the effects of the political crisis from an integrated approach between *polity*, *politics*, and *policy*. Instead of taking these dimensions as hierarchically arranged or as exogenous variables to each other, the article proposes to understand them as interdependent and mutually constitutive instances. The Brazilian crisis has shown that not only does politics influence institutions, but that institutions also condition political games and that the definition of public policies, as well as the dispute surrounding them, can in turn feed back into and alter institutional arrangements and patterns of interaction between actors. This understanding requires going beyond one-dimensional explanations and observing

the multiplicity of causalities and cross-effects that shape the functioning of democratic systems under stress. The Brazilian case's contribution to comparative politics lies decisively in the way that *polity*, *politics*, and *policy* interact here in periods of stability but also in times of regime crisis.

Consequently, by proposing this explanatory model, the article contributes to enriching comparative studies on democratic crises, offering an interpretative key capable of dealing with different degrees of institutional transformation, whether through rupture, adaptation, or resilience. Based on an analysis of Brazilian democracy between 2012 and 2025, we have demonstrated how interactions between actors, institutions, and public policies were able to produce varied responses to the crisis, sometimes deepening institutional erosion, sometimes activating mechanisms of containment and recomposition. This perspective offers a fertile analytical tool for understanding not only the Brazilian case, but one that can be replicated and useful for the comparative analysis of other contemporary experiences in which democracies are put to the test at multiple levels and with varying degrees of intensity.

In short, the period analyzed represented important transformations in Brazilian political governance, with significant changes in the areas of government, justice, and federalism. Although the predominance of coalition presidentialism gave rise to weakened presidencies or those that abandoned the old pattern of governance (some even considering institutional rupture), it is worth noting that democratic resilience was based on the consensual arrangement adopted by the 1988 constitutional model, but remained secondary and less crucial to democracy during the period of strong and successful presidencies. Thus, the democratic regime, built over decades in the post-1988 period, proved resilient and survived President Bolsonaro's attempts to erode democracy and, ultimately, stage a *coup d'état*.

On the other hand, there have been institutional changes in dominant political behaviors and public policy patterns. In the areas of budgeting and the functioning of the electoral and party systems, these changes have been elevated to constitutional status through amendments, but also through constitutional review by the country's supreme court, intensifying successive rounds involving *politics*, *policy*, and *polity*, as demonstrated in the analysis developed in this article. However, it cannot be said that these changes have generated a stable paradigm such as the one Brazil had, especially between 1993 and 2012. In this new scenario, the instability of the political system has strongly affected the Lula III government, and it remains to be seen whether the reaction to authoritarian and anti-systemic behaviors, which continue to be present, mobilized by the extreme right (including international alliances), will be able to generate a new institutionality and guarantee Brazilian democratic governance in the coming years.

AI usage statement

All ideas and arguments presented in this article were developed by the authors, without the use of AI tools. The text was translated into English using the DeepL tool and then reviewed by the authors.

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Data availability statement

Data is available in the body of the article.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest that could have influenced the preparation of this article.

Cláudio Gonçalves Couto (claudio.couto@fgv.br) holds a PhD in Political Science from USP and is a professor in the Department of Public Management at FGV EAESP.

Rogério Bastos Arantes (rarantes@usp.br) holds a PhD in Political Science from USP and is a professor in the Department of Political Science at USP.

Fernando Luiz Abrucio (fernando.abrucio@fgv.br) holds a PhD in Political Science from USP and is a professor in the Department of Public Management at FGV EAESP.

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Transformação e resiliência institucional na democracia brasileira (2012-2025): *Polity*, *Politics* e *Policy* em interação

Palavras-chave: presidencialismo de coalizão, ativismo judicial, federalismo, mudança institucional, resiliência institucional.

RESUMO Introdução: Entre 2012 e 2025, a democracia brasileira enfrentou crises que testaram os pilares do presidencialismo, do sistema de justiça e do federalismo. Este artigo analisa como essas tensões produziram mudanças institucionais e revelaram a resiliência do regime. O argumento central é que a compreensão da democracia sob estresse exige articular três dimensões: *polity* (as regras e instituições que estruturam o regime), *politics* (a competição política e os conflitos entre atores) e *policy* (as decisões e resultados das políticas públicas). **Materiais e métodos:** Adota-se a abordagem institucionalista histórica, com uso de process tracing para identificar mecanismos causais que conectam eventos críticos, escolhas institucionais e mudanças de comportamento dos atores. O período 2012-2025 é examinado a partir das arenas do sistema de governo, do sistema de justiça e das relações federativas. **Resultados:** Três transformações principais foram observadas. No sistema de governo, o Congresso Nacional ampliou seu poder de veto e de formulação, sobretudo via controle orçamentário, consolidando um “governo congressional”. No sistema de justiça, o Supremo Tribunal Federal expandiu seu protagonismo: redesenhou regras político-eleitorais, julgou o Mensalão e conteve iniciativas autoritárias do bolsonarismo, inclusive garantindo competências de estados e municípios. No federalismo, sem reformas formais, governos subnacionais assumiram protagonismo, especialmente durante a pandemia, reforçando capacidades autônomas e cooperação interfederativa, mas também aprofundando desigualdades territoriais. **Discussão:** As crises políticas entre 2012 e 2025 não apenas tensionaram, mas também fortaleceram as instituições, ao gerar adaptações duradouras e aprendizado institucional. A interação entre *polity*, *politics* e *policy* remodelou o sistema político formal e informalmente, revelando resiliência democrática mesmo em cenários de risco de golpe de Estado. Esse modelo interpretativo contribui para estudos comparados sobre como democracias sob estresse podem resistir e se transformar.

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